

THE IMPORTANCE OF NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN LESSONS

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ANNOTATION

In the field of education, the use of pedagogical and information and communication technologies, Internet information and educational resources, and the conference method will effectively help students to acquire knowledge at a high level and create an opportunity for them to become qualified specialists in the future.

Key words: pedagogical technology, auxiliary teaching aids, technical means of teaching, modern information technologies, independent education.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the time of traditional lectures based only on lectures has passed. At a time when the speed of the flow of information is accelerating, it is difficult to attract the student's attention to knowledge if every lesson is not colorful. For this, the teacher needs to constantly search and be creative. In this case, it is especially effective to pass the lesson based on the game-based viewing system. Games should be chosen based on the student's psychology. The method of encouraging to be the first always pays off. Because children always want to show themselves, to be one step ahead of their peers. The main basis of pedagogical technology is the technology chosen for the cooperation of the teacher and the student to achieve a guaranteed result from the set goal. Each educational technology used in the teaching process to achieve a guaranteed result according to the goal should be able to organize cooperation between the teacher and the student, both of them should be able to achieve a positive result, the student in the learning process Students should be able to think independently, work creatively, research, analyze, draw their own conclusions, evaluate themselves, the group, and the group, and the teacher should create opportunities and conditions for such activities. is the basis of the process.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

In the process of researching this article, the methods of logic, consistency, historicity and objectivity of scientific knowledge were widely used. The role of modern pedagogical technologies in teaching professional terminological vocabulary was objectively revealed. The period of development of pedagogical technologies was analyzed from the point of view of history. N.I. Taylakov's study guide "Prospects of implementing modern information technologies in the educational system" was used as a methodological source.

Synectics method. This method is practical, suitable for seminars and laboratory exercises, and is close to the "brainstorming" method. In this case, the student puts forward his thoughts and views on the solution of the problem set in the lesson, based on analogy. In this case, the analogy can be direct, personal, symbolic and imaginary.

"Round table" method. This method is convenient for practical training. In this, the teacher presents a sheet with one question to the small group. Students write their names and answers to the question and pass the sheet to the student next to them. The answers written in

this way are collected, wrong ones are deleted with the participation of students and the results are evaluated.

"Pen on the table" method. This method is suitable for practical training. A student in a small group, who has written his answer to the question, puts his pen on the table and passes the sheet to his partner. A student who cannot write an answer to a question does not put his pen on the table.

CONCLUSION

- The advantages of using modern information technologies in the educational process are as follows:

- deeper and more perfect assimilation of the materials given in the educational process;
- introduction of new forms of education;
- opportunity to save time as a result of reduction of learning time in the course of the lesson;
- acquired knowledge can be retained in a person's memory for a long time and can be applied in practice.
- the shortness of time for students to develop certain skills;
- increase in the number of tasks performed in training;
- as a result of requiring active control by the computer, the student becomes an educational subject, etc.

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